

Sample 25a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0052
	{Si}	58.5
	{Al, Si}	9.4
	{Fe}	7.8
	{Al, Si, K}	4.5
	{Ca}	3.6
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.8
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.3
	{Al, Si, Ca}	2.0
	{Si, Fe}	1.4
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.1
	{Mg, Ca}	0.7
	{Na, Si}	0.7
	{Si, K}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.5
	{S, Ca}	0.4
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Mn}	0.3
	{Ti}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Si, Fe}	0.3
	{P, Ca}	0.2
	{Al}	0.2
	{Mn, Fe}	0.2
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Ti, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Ti}	0.1
	{Zn-LA1}	0.1
	{Ca, Ti}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.3
Pellet	2.8
Ore preparation undifferentiated	3.9
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.4
Ore / hot metal	0.2
BOF converter slag	1.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.4
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.4
Desulph slag	0.3
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.6
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.1
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.1
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	13.1
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.8
Carbon rich - other	2.1
Cement or BOF converter	0.5
Cement	2.4
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.2
Ti-rich paint	0.6
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.1
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-day-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	59.7
Qz-day-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	8.0
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.2
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.6
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	7.5
Site - ore / hot metal	0.2
Site - slag	2.3
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.6
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.1
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.1
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	13.1
Site - carbon-rich other	0.8
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	2.1
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.5
Urban	3.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	59.7
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	8.0
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.2
Unknown	0.6
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 25b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0047
	{Si}	52.6
	{Fe}	14.2
	{Al, Si}	10.6
	{Al, Si, K}	3.2
	{Ca}	2.8
	{Na, Al, Si}	2.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.0
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.9
	{Si, Fe}	1.9
	{Si, Ca HiP}	0.9
	{Si, K}	0.7
	{Ca, Fe}	0.7
	{Na, Si}	0.6
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.5
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.4
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Al, Ca}	0.3
	{Ti}	0.3
	{Al}	0.3
	{Mg, Ca}	0.3
	{Si, Fe}	0.2
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{S, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Fe}	0.2
	{Cl}	0.1
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Zn-LA1}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Al, Fe}	0.1
	{S}	0.1
	{Na, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Ti}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	2.1
Pellet	3.1
Ore preparation undifferentiated	7.8
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	1.0
BOF converter slag	0.4
BOF converter slag slopping	0.2
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.1
Desulph slag	0.2
Ca-aluminate slag	0.3
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.1
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.6
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.2
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	15.7
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.2
Carbon rich - other	2.3
Cement or BOF converter	0.7
Cement	2.0
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.5
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	52.9
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	7.1
Misc silicates including natural	0.1
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.2
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.2

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	12.9
Site - ore / hot metal	1.0
Site - slag	2.1
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.2
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.6
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.2
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	15.7
Site - carbon-rich other	1.2
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	2.3
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.7
Urban	2.6
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	52.9
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	7.1
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.2
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.2

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 25c

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0060
	{Si}	57.2
	{Al, Si}	10.9
	{Fe}	7.9
	{Ca}	4.8
	{Na, Al, Si}	3.0
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.7
	{Al, Si, K}	2.3
	{Al, Si, Ca}	2.3
	{Si, Fe}	1.2
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.2
	{Si, K}	0.7
	{Mg, Si}	0.6
	{Na, Si}	0.6
	{Cl}	0.5
	{Ti}	0.3
	{Ca, Fe}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.3
	{Si, Fe}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Al}	0.2
	{S, Ca}	0.2
	{Al, Cl}	0.2
	{Al, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Ca}	0.2
	{Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Na, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{P, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{S}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Fe}	0.1
	{Al, Si, P}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.8
Pellet	1.8
Ore preparation undifferentiated	2.4
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.4
BOF converter slag	0.6
BOF converter slag slopping	0.7
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.1
Desulph slag	0.4
Ca-aluminate slag	0.1
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.2
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.8
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	23.9
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.7
Carbon rich - other	3.2
Cement or BOF converter	1.1
Cement	2.4
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.2
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.4
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.2
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	48.1
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	8.7
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.2
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.5

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	5.0
Site - ore / hot metal	0.4
Site - slag	2.0
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.2
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.8
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	23.9
Site - carbon-rich other	1.7
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	3.2
Urban; rarely site - slag	1.1
Urban	3.1
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	48.1
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	8.7
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.2
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels